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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
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**8-Constitutional Rights and Freedoms of
Citizens: Problems of Protection And
Implementation In Ukraine. By Denys
Chyzhov . And others. p. 154.**

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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
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**A GROUP OF UNIVERSITY GRADUATES IN UKRAINE
PREPARED**

**CENTER FOR LAW AND POLITICAL RESEARCH – DENMARK
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Contents of Vol. No. (47/2) of Issue October-2025

- 1- **International Security Cooperation of Ukraine in The Face of The Russian-Ukrainian War: Factors of Historical and Legal Aspects.** By Yurii Rusnak and others. p. 10.
- 2- **Global Strategic Rivalry and the Secure Architecture: Nato's Influence on The Formation of The International Peace,** By Yevhenii Taran. and others. p. 30.
- 3- **Multipolarity of the Global Space: Strategic Understanding of Geopolitical Trends.** By Viacheslav Kolotov and others. p. 55.
- 4- **Mechanisms for Restoring Violated Rights to Intellectual Products: Law Enforcement Difficulties in Ukraine.** By Viktoriia Kobko-Odarii and others. p. 82.
- 5- **Civic Engagement as a Driver of Political Change in Post-Totalitarian States.** Vitalii Kostenko and others. p. 104.
- 6- **International Humanitarian Law Implications During the War in Ukraine: Problems and Violations.** By Oleksandr Khomenko and others. p. 123.
- 7- **Russian-Ukrainian War's Geopolitical Consequences for Eastern Europe.** By Vira Kazymir and others. p. 138.
- 8- **Constitutional Rights and Freedoms of Citizens: Problems of Protection And Implementation In Ukraine.** By Denys Chyzhov . And others. P. 154.
- 9- **Criminal Liability for Economic Crimes: Issues of Legal Qualification And Application In Practice.** By Volodymyr Myslyvyy and others. p. 176.
- 10- **The Dynamics of Public-Private Interaction in Advancing Sustainable Development Through Investment Strategies and Administration.** By Myroslav Buryk and others. p. 198.
- 11- **Cooperation of Governmental Institutions And Advocacy Associations Within the Framework of The Fundamental Freedoms: Conceptual Perspective.** By Olena Bondarchuk- Ladna and others. p. 228.
- 12- **The Issue of Criminal Liability for Corruption Crimes in The Context of Legal Modernization.** By Anfisa Serhiienko and others. p. 250.
- 13- **Anti-Corruption Policy and Its Administration in Public Administration: Theoretical Foundations and Practical Aspects of the Legal Framework.** By Oleksii Vasyliiev and others. p. 276.
- 14- **Electoral Behavioral Models in Sweden and Norway: A Psychopolitical Perspective.** By Viktor Melnyk and others. p. 299.
- 15- **The Evolution of Legal Frameworks in Lithuanian State Formation: Historical Perspectives -and The Impact of European Integration.** By Lesia Kotsur and others. p. 325.
- 16- **Public Debt and Public Debt Administration Under Martial Law in the Process of Post-War Reconstruction,** By Serhii Petrukha and others. p. 341.
- 17- **Global Economic Interaction as a Factor of Innovative Progress in Countries with A Transformational Model of Growth.** By Yevhenii Kostyk and others. p. 372,

(8)

CONSTITUTIONAL RIGHTS AND FREEDOMS OF CITIZENS: PROBLEMS OF PROTECTION AND IMPLEMENTATION IN UKRAINE

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ABSTRACT

The article provides a comprehensive study of the constitutional rights and freedoms of Ukrainian citizens under martial law, which is extremely relevant in light of the full-scale armed aggression against Ukraine. The paper explores the

conceptual and legal foundations of key human rights and freedoms as outlined in Ukraine's Constitution, with reference to global legal principles. Particular attention is paid to the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the 1950 European Convention on Human Rights. An in-depth evaluation of governmental strategies and approaches within the relevant sector of human rights during the war is carried out, focusing on the problems of ensuring freedom of speech, the rights of prisoners of war, internally displaced persons, restrictions on religious freedom and judicial protection. Special focus is given to examining the legal framework, including laws on martial law, restrictive measures, and procedures for the realization of citizens' rights under a special regime. The article also examines the reports of international human rights organizations, such as OHCHR and Human Rights Watch, in order to verify the facts of human rights violations in the occupied and controlled territories. The study is based on an interdisciplinary approach that combines elements of constitutional. As a result, the author formulates conclusions regarding the need to improve legal regulation, ensure effective control over ensuring respect for fundamental human freedoms, and develop a national mechanism for their protection in the post-war period. The author suggests the ways to improve the human rights policy of the State, taking into account the challenges of wartime and the prospects for peaceful restoration.

Keywords: constitutional rights, human freedoms, legal protection, Ukraine, international humanitarian law, legal restrictions.

1- INTRODUCTION

The constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens are fundamental categories of the modern legal order that ensure the integration of a person into the system of state power based on the rule of law. They are enshrined in the text of the state's core legal framework, the Constitution, and have the highest legal force. Legally speaking theory, these rights are inalienable, universal and of high priority, as they embody the values of human dignity, freedom, equality and justice. Constitutional rights are usually divided into civil (personal), political, socio-economic, cultural and environmental rights. They have both subjective and objective content: on the one hand, they guarantee opportunities for realization for each person, and on the other hand, they form the state's obligations to ensure and protect these opportunities. The definition of such rights is universal, which is confirmed by international acts, in particular the UDHR¹, which sets basic standards of the legal status of man and citizen for all states of the world.

In Ukraine, the system of constitutional rights and freedoms was historically formed as part of the democratic social contract after the declaration of independence, and is legally enshrined in the 1996 Constitution. The main provisions are contained in Section II, which establishes a list of rights, their guarantees and possible restrictions. At

¹ United Nations General Assembly. (1948). *Universal Declaration of Human Rights*. https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_015#Text

the same time, the Ukrainian reality is characterized by complex challenges related to the long-term military assault by the Russian Federation and partial territorial seizure and the introduction of martial law. In such circumstances, the exercise of constitutional rights is significantly affected by restrictive measures provided for in the Constitution (Article 64), but in practice require compliance with the principle of proportionality. The imposition of curfews or restrictions on freedom of assembly, according to Cabinet of Ministers Resolution No. 573², is a necessary security measure, but should be implemented with due process and under external oversight by human rights institutions. Problems arise in access to judicial protection, freedom of religion and expression, which necessitates the improvement of national legislation in line with international standards.

Ukraine is currently at the stage of forming a stable rule-of-law state, which should guarantee formal recognition of human rights and their effective realization and protection – even in times of war. In this context, the interaction of national legislation with international standards, primarily Europe’s primary legal instrument for rights protection³, which takes precedence over national law and is part of the legal order of Ukraine, is extremely important. One of the main challenges is to strike a balance between the needs of state security priorities and its commitment to guarantee the principles of legal certainty, non-discrimination and respect for human dignity. This is especially true under martial law, when the exercise of many rights may be temporarily restricted but not abolished. A law-based state should develop legal mechanisms that allow for a prompt confront the impacts of war and provide control over the actions of the authorities and access to justice for all categories of citizens. It is important that these mechanisms do not lose their effectiveness after the active phase of the conflict is over, but become the basis for further democratization and integration of Ukraine into the EU legal system.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Basic constitutional guarantees afforded to citizens remain one of the key topics for research regarding human rights issues, especially in the context of socio-political turbulence. Modern scholarly works focus on the theoretical and legal dimension and on

² Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine. (2020). *Procedure for implementing measures during the imposition of curfew and establishment of special light masking regime in certain areas under martial law*. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/573-2020-#Text>

³ Council of Europe. (1950). *Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms*. https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_004#Text

the applied aspects of the realization of rights in times of war, reform dynamics under emergency or military-led governance national legislation in accordance with international standards. Particular attention is paid to the role of the judicial system, application of law by authorities, and the impact of external aggression on the system of legal protection of citizens.

Muraviov and Mushak⁴ focuses on the legal problems of implementing the ECHR in the Ukrainian legal field, in particular in terms of the priority of international law. Leheza et al.⁵ examine human rights mechanisms in the social and legal spheres, pointing to the imbalance between constitutional norms and the actual practice of their enforcement. Butenko et al.⁶ raise the important issue of the abuse of forensic psychiatric examinations in administrative proceedings, which directly affects the rights of citizens to protection, liberty and a fair trial.

Shevchuk et al.⁷ analyze the problems of forensic examination in matters of public health care as part of human rights, emphasizing the need for legal regulation of the participation of experts in human rights processes. The study by Qaisrani et al.⁸ shows geopolitical challenges for Ukraine that directly affect the realization of human rights, in particular due to military aggression. In turn, Dzhuska et al.⁹ emphasize the evolution of the concept with respect to life preservation rights, interpreting it against the backdrop of armed conflict and medical challenges.

Myshlovska¹⁰ analyzes the narrative dynamics of the conflict between Russia and Ukraine through the prism of international human rights organizations, pointing to the

⁴ Muraviov, V., & Mushak, N. (2021). Legal issues of the implementation of the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms 1950 in Ukraine. *Access to Justice in Eastern Europe*, 4(1), 8–22. <https://doi.org/10.33327/AJEE-18-4.1-n000044>

⁵ Leheza, Y., Filipenko, T., Sokolenko, O., Darahan, V., & Kucherenko, O. (2020). Ensuring Human Rights in Ukraine: Problematic Issues and Ways of their Solution in the Social and Legal Sphere. *Cuestiones Políticas*, 37(64), 124–136. <https://doi.org/10.46398/custpol.3764.10>

⁶ Butenko, D., Dimitrova, S., & Gröning, L. (2023). Identifying deficits in Ukrainian law: Forensic psychiatry misuse in proceedings of administrative offenses. *International Journal of Law and Psychiatry*, 90, 101920. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijlp.2023.101920>

⁷ Shevchuk, O., Matyukhina, N., Davydenko, S., Babaieva, O., & Lysodyed, O. (2022). Forensic examination in cases on the protection of human rights in the sphere of healthcare in Ukraine: legal issues. *Juridical Tribune*, 12(4), 552–565. <https://doi.org/10.24818/tbj/2022/12/4.08>

⁸ Qaisrani, I., Qazi, B., & Abbas, H. (2023). A Geopolitical War in Europe: Russia's Invasion of Ukraine and its Implications. *Journal of European Studies (JES)*, 39(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.56384/jes.v39i1.285>

⁹ Dzhuska, A. V., Kaminska, N. V., & Makarukha, Z. M. (2021). Modern concept of understanding the human right to life. *Wiadomosci Lekarskie*, 74(2), 341–350. <https://doi.org/10.36740/wlek202102131>

¹⁰ Myshlovska, O. (2022). Conflict dynamics as a narrative process: The evolution of competing conflict narratives between Russia and Ukraine and the narratives of the international human rights bodies between 2014 and 2022. *Central European Journal of International and Security Studies*, 16(3), 76–107. <https://doi.org/10.51870/GDIM2629>

formation of alternative discourses. Anisimova and Kopytsia¹¹ examine the role of courts in ensuring environmental rights, emphasizing the lack of effectiveness of judicial protection. Dzhafarova et al.¹² examine the administrative and legal mechanisms for the realization concerning citizens' rights and liberties under the jurisdiction of the Security Service of Ukraine, with a focus on systemic violations.

Honcharenko et al.¹³ expand on the topic of corporate social responsibility as a component of human rights in wartime, emphasizing its non-state dimension. Shamrai et al.¹⁴ highlight the use of ECHR case law in Ukrainian criminal procedure, demonstrating the gradual adaptation of Ukrainian courts to European standards.

Romtsiv¹⁵ focuses on international mechanisms of legal protection in times of war. Pattison¹⁶ analyzes interference in Ukraine's affairs through the lens of the liberal order, questioning the effectiveness of the international legal system. Zolka et al.¹⁷ examine the consequences of COVID-19 for the freedom of movement of citizens, considering the restriction of rights in emergency circumstances as a test of the effectiveness of the constitutional protection mechanism.

Thus, the literature analysis shows a systemic interest in human rights in Ukraine, both at the level of national legislation and from the perspective of international law. Existing research points to the complex interplay between Ukraine's legal obligations and real-world challenges that require further legal adaptation and institutional transformation.

Research objectives. This article aims to thoroughly examine the implementation and protection of constitutional entitlements and liberties of Ukrainian citizens under

¹¹ Anisimova, H., & Kopytsia, I. (2021). The role of courts in environmental rights protection in the context of the state policy of Ukraine. *Access to Justice in Eastern Europe*, 4(2), 164–176. <https://doi.org/10.33327/AJEE-18-4.2-N000066>

¹² Dzhafarova, O., Shatrava, S., & Leshchenko, D. (2024). Administrative and legal provision of human and citizen rights and freedoms by the Security Service of Ukraine: Today's issues. *Scientific Notes Series Law*, 1(15), 42–46. <https://doi.org/10.36550/2522-9230-2023-15-42-46>

¹³ Honcharenko, O., Neskoro dzhen a, L., Iefremova, I., Lomakina, I., & Malyshko, I. (2022). Development of the concept of corporate social responsibility: Practice in Ukraine. *Comparative Law Review*, 28, 367–392. <https://doi.org/10.12775/CLR.2022.012>

¹⁴ Shamrai, V. V., Ivchuk, Y. Y., Tarasenko, V. Y., & Fedorov, H. O. (2020). Topical Issues of the Application of the Case-Law of the European Court of Human Rights in the Criminal Process of Ukraine. *Revista Amazonia Investiga*, 9(29), 6–14. <https://doi.org/10.34069/ai/2020.29.05.1>

¹⁵ Romtsiv, O. I. (2023). International legal mechanisms for the protection of human rights and freedoms in times of war: the practice of the ECHR. *Analytical and Comparative Jurisprudence*, 6, 168–172. <https://doi.org/10.24144/2788-6018.2023.06.29>

¹⁶ Pattison, J. (2022). *Ukraine, Intervention, and the Post-Liberal Order. Ethics and International Affairs*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0892679422000399>

¹⁷ Zolka, V., Tsarenko, O., Kushnir, I., Tsarenko, S., & Havrik, R. (2021). The impact of the pandemic COVID-19 on the human right to freedom of movement. *European Journal of Sustainable Development*, 10(1), 376–388. <https://doi.org/10.14207/ejsd.2021.v10n1p376>

the state of military governance regime, and to identify the key legal, institutional and practical issues arising in matters related to individual freedoms during an armed conflict. Particular attention is paid to the legal content and theoretical understanding of constitutional rights, the specifics of their restriction, and the mechanisms of state and international control over their observance. The article analyzes national legal acts, international legal obligations of Ukraine, reports of human rights organizations and the practice of public authorities in ensuring human rights in crisis conditions. The study aims to highlight the challenges that will arise in the post-war period, including the issues of legal rehabilitation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research procedure involved a step-by-step analytical approach to studying constitutionally protected freedoms of individuals in Ukraine under martial law. At the first stage, the body of laws governing the exercise of information on human rights during martial law was gathered – the Constitution of Ukraine, laws on the legal foundations of military-administered authority, bylaws of the Cabinet of Ministers, decrees of the President of Ukraine, international legal sources¹⁸. Next, reports from global institutions for human rights protection, including OHCHR and Human Rights Watch, were reviewed to identify practical violations and challenges. The final stage included a review of rights issues environment, trends and prospects in the post-war period, with a focus on the transformation of legal mechanisms and potential models for recovery.

The selection of sources covered key Ukrainian laws regulating human rights during martial law on the implementation of restrictive measures, along with the constitutional norms of Ukraine (Section II). Particular attention is paid to the provisions that cause debate in academic circles, such as Article 35 (right to freedom of conscience) and restrictions on freedom of religion, Article 64 on the possibility of restricting rights in wartime, and provisions on “collaborationism”. The sample included scientific literature analyzing the Ukrainian experience in the area of the balance between security and human rights, comparative studies on democratic standards.

To ensure a comprehensive analysis, several qualitative research methods were used. First of all, a doctrinal (dogmatic) analysis of national and international law on the realization of human rights and freedoms was carried out. Next, the method of critical legal analysis was applied to the official reports of OHCHR¹⁹, Human Rights Watch²⁰,

¹⁸ President of Ukraine. (2022). *On the introduction of martial law in Ukraine: Decree No. 64/2022 of February 24, 2022 (with amendments)*. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/64/2022#Text>

¹⁹ Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR). (2024, December 31). *Report on the Human Rights Situation in Ukraine: 1 September to 30 November 2024*. <https://ukraine.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/2024-12/PR41%20Ukraine%202024-12-31.pdf>

²⁰ Human Rights Watch. (2024). *Ukraine: Events of 2023*. In *World Report 2024*. <https://www.hrw.org/world-report/2024/country-chapters/ukraine>

the Ukrainian Parliament Commissioner for Human Rights (Ombudsman)²¹, alongside the rulings of the Constitutional Court of Ukraine. The content analysis of international law documents (UDHR, ECHR) was used to identify compliance or discrepancies in the application of global legal norms. The method of structural-functional analysis was used to study the system of human rights realization, and the comparative legal approach allowed to analyze the legal regulation of similar situations in the EU countries.

In general, the research methodology is based on an interdisciplinary approach that combines legal, human rights, and political and legal analysis. This approach ensured objectivity and depth in revealing the problem of realization of constitutional rights in times of crisis, in studying the possibilities of institutional restoration of human rights in the post-war period. The research methodology reveals systemic problems in the regulation of rights and forms the analytical basis for further reforms, taking into account international standards and experience rights practices in the state of emergency.

2. RESULTS

2.1. THE STATE OF REALIZATION OF CONSTITUTIONAL RIGHTS AND FREEDOMS OF CITIZENS UNDER MARTIAL LAW

2.1.1. CONSTITUTIONAL RIGHTS OF CITIZENS OF UKRAINE AND THEIR RESTRICTIONS IN TIME OF WAR

Constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens are fundamental components of law, defining the limits of state power and guaranteeing human dignity. In Ukraine, the provisions are enshrined in Section II of the Constitution, which guarantees a wide range of rights: from the right to life and religion and peaceful assembly. A particular threat is posed by human rights violations both in the occupied territories and in the context of mobilization, restrictions on freedom of speech and religion, and problems in the field of justice.

Reports by international organizations have identified numerous cases of excessive or unlawful restrictions. OHCHR²² points to serious violations of the rights of prisoners of war, cases of torture and sexual violence on both sides of the conflict. Such

²¹ Ukrainian Parliament Commissioner for Human Rights (Ombudsman). (2022). *The constitutional right of citizens to appeal under martial law conditions*. https://www.ombudsman.gov.ua/news_details/konstitucijne-pravo-gromadyan-na-zvernennya-v-umovah-voyennogo-stanu

²² Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR). (2024, December 31). *Report on the Human Rights Situation in Ukraine: 1 September to 30 November 2024*. <https://ukraine.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/2024-12/PR41%20Ukraine%202024-12-31.pdf>

Freedom of religion (art. 35)	Restriction only under conditions provided by law	Prohibition of activities of religious organizations associated with the Russian Federation; potential threat to the UOC
Right to a fair trial (arts. 55, 129)	Guarantee of an independent and fair hearing	Detention of prisoners without access to lawyers, coercion to self-incrimination, conviction for participation in hostilities
Freedom of expression (art. 34)	May be limited by law, if necessary	Administrative and criminal persecution in the temporarily occupied regions for Ukrainian symbols, music, and statements
Right to education and cultural identity (arts. 53, 11)	The state guarantees access to education	In the occupied territories, the Russian Federation implements the Russian curriculum and imposes “military-patriotic” education on children
Right to association (art. 36) and peaceful assembly (art. 39)	Protected by law	In the occupied territories, there is a complete ban on peaceful protests; in the government-controlled territories, there are restrictions due to martial law

Source: compiled on the basis on²⁵

Ukraine’s system of law has been faced with the task of maintaining a balance between security challenges and the state’s human rights obligations. According to Article 64 of the Constitution of Ukraine, certain rights can be limited under emergency or wartime conditions, but these restrictions must not contradict the state’s international obligations²⁶. At the same time, Article 15 of the European Convention on Human

²⁵ Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR). (2024). *Report on the Human Rights Situation in Ukraine: 1 September to 30 November 2024*. <https://ukraine.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/2024-12/PR41%20Ukraine%202024-12-31.pdf>

²⁶ Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. (1996). *Rights, Freedoms and Duties of a Person and a Citizen (Articles 21–68)*. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/254%D0%BA/96-%D0%B2%D1%80#Text>

Rights forbids the suspension of specific core rights, including the right to life, protection against torture, slavery and discrimination, even in a state of emergency²⁷.

The effectiveness of these measures largely depends on whether they are accompanied by legal safeguards to protect citizens. In the context of prolonged restrictions on movement, internally displaced persons, people with disabilities and residents of frontline areas often face limited access to legal aid.

2.2. PROSPECTS FOR THE RESTORATION AND PROTECTION OF CONSTITUTIONAL RIGHTS IN THE POST-WAR PERIOD

2.2.1. PRIORITIES FOR LEGAL INTEGRATION AND JUSTICE AFTER THE WAR

One of the key problems has been legal uncertainty in the area of ensuring the right to appeal. The Ombudsman of Ukraine points out that despite the existence of the constitutional right of citizens to appeal, the mechanisms for its implementation during the war remain limited, in particular due to inadequate communication between the authorities in the regions of hostilities and in the occupied territories²⁸. In the context of the armed conflict, it is necessary to create mobile and remote tools for filing appeals and complaints, especially for vulnerable groups.

The issue of distinguishing between security and freedom of speech deserves special attention. Human Rights Watch²⁹ draws attention to cases where the state has resorted to blocking certain media outlets or restricting content without proper judicial oversight. Such actions can undermine trust in institutions, even if they are justified by security concerns.

Another area of legal tension is ensuring equal access to education and healthcare in wartime. Although the Constitution guarantees the right to education (Article 53) and medical care (Article 49), in practice many citizens were deprived of these rights due to the destruction of infrastructure and insufficient adaptation of public services to the war.

²⁷ Council of Europe. (1950). *Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms*. https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_004#Text

²⁸ Ukrainian Parliament Commissioner for Human Rights (Ombudsman). (2022). *The constitutional right of citizens to appeal under martial law conditions*. https://www.ombudsman.gov.ua/news_details/konstitucijne-pravo-gromadyan-na-zvernennya-v-umovah-voyennogo-stanu

²⁹ Human Rights Watch. (2024). *Ukraine: Events of 2023*. In *World Report 2024*. <https://www.hrw.org/world-report/2024/country-chapters/ukraine>

The main problematic aspects of the observance of the rights and freedoms of citizens are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Analysis of the problems of realization of constitutional rights of citizens during martial law and prospects for the post-war period

The problem of implementation	OHCHR legal assessment (2024)	Prospects after the war
Restrictions on movement and assembly	Temporary measures should be proportionate; review of restriction mechanisms is needed.	Restoration of assemblies, renewal of guarantees of freedom, taking into account security.
The right to appeal to the authorities	Remote channels of appeal are needed, especially for IDPs.	Expansion of electronic services, simplification of access.
Persecution for “collaborationism”	Individualization and consideration of coercion are required.	Review of cases, amnesty mechanisms, reconciliation commissions.
Restrictions on religious freedom	Some provisions contradict international standards.	Dialogue with communities, ensuring religious pluralism.
Conscientious objection to military service	There are no mechanisms for mobilization, which is a violation of the Constitution.	Introduction of alternative service even during the mobilization period.
Restrictions on freedom of speech and blocking of media	There is a risk of disproportionate interference; restrictions without trial.	Independent media regulation, reform of information legislation.
Access to education and healthcare in the war zones	Basic rights to education and medical care are not ensured.	Restoration of infrastructure, development of remote services.
Lack of access to courts in the occupied territories	Temporary legal formats for uncontrolled regions are needed.	Remote justice, adaptation of the system to the conditions of reintegration.

Source: developed on the basis on^{30, 31, 32}

After the active phase of the armed conflict is over, Ukraine will enter a new phase of reconstruction, reintegration and the reestablishment of legal order. One of the key tasks will be the reintegration of the occupied territories, which involves ensuring equal access to justice, medical, social and administrative services for citizens who were under the jurisdiction of another state or de facto authorities. It is especially important to prevent discrimination on the basis of residence or actions taken under duress, which directly follows from the provisions of international humanitarian law^{33, 34}.

2.2.2. LEGAL REFORMS, EUROPEAN INTEGRATION AND NEW MECHANISMS FOR ENSURING RIGHTS AND FREEDOMS

The legal rehabilitation of victims of war crimes and conflict violence will be a global challenge³⁵. The issues of compensation, access to psychological assistance, and transitional justice mechanisms (e.g., the establishment of commissions to investigate torture, sexual violence, and illegal detention) should be enshrined in law. Ukraine currently lacks a law on transitional justice, although such a model has been successfully implemented in a number of countries that have experienced armed conflict (examples include Colombia, Rwanda, and South Africa).

Restoration of trust in state institutions, which was destroyed during the war due to restrictions on rights, excessive concentration of power and ineffective response to crisis situations, remains a problematic issue. According to the Constitutional Court of Ukraine, in a democratic legal order, even in a state of emergency, the principle of accountability of the authorities to the people is valid³⁶. Therefore, it is advisable to

³⁰ Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR). (2024). *Report on the Human Rights Situation in Ukraine: 1 September to 30 November 2024*. <https://ukraine.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/2024-12/PR41%20Ukraine%202024-12-31.pdf>

³¹ Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. (1996). *Constitution of Ukraine. Section II: Rights, Freedoms and Duties of a Person and a Citizen*. <https://www.president.gov.ua/ua/documents/constitution/konstituciya-ukrayini-rozdil-ii>

³² Human Rights Watch. (2024). *Ukraine: Events of 2023*. In *World Report 2024*. <https://www.hrw.org/world-report/2024/country-chapters/ukraine>

³³ Council of Europe. (1950). *Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms*. https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_004#Text

³⁴ United Nations General Assembly. (1948). *Universal Declaration of Human Rights*. https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_015#Text

³⁵ Azarov, D., Koval, D., Nuridzhanian, G., & Venher, V. (2023). Understanding Russia's Actions in Ukraine as the Crime of Genocide. *Journal of International Criminal Justice*, 21(2), 233–264. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jicj/mqad018>

³⁶ Constitutional Court of Ukraine. (n.d.). *Rights, Freedoms and Duties of a Person and a Citizen*. <https://ccu.gov.ua/storinka-knygy/4-prava-svobody-i-obovyazky-lyudyny-i-gromadyanyna>

provide for independent monitoring of human rights after the war, for example, through the establishment of a parliamentary human rights commission.

Millions of citizens who have lost their homes, jobs, or health need legal protection in terms of compensation for damages, social housing, access to education, and retraining. Articles 21-22 of the Constitution of Ukraine proclaim equality of rights regardless of circumstances, but the realization of this principle will require targeted government programs and special legislation³⁷.

The task will be to harmonize Ukrainian legislation with international standards, in particular in terms of ensuring freedom of thought, religion, peaceful assembly and conscientious objection. Special attention will be required to implement all the provisions the ECHR judgments that were temporarily suspended during the war. Legal reform is the basis for the protection of human rights and for Ukraine's European integration in peace.

The protection and realization of the constitutional rights of citizens have become critically important and have revealed a number of profound legal and humanitarian problems. The study shows that despite the efforts of the state, international organizations and human rights institutions. In particular, numerous cases of rights violations in the occupied territories, problems with the right to alternative service, persecution for collaboration, and difficulties in guaranteeing the rights of IDPs point to the need for a profound legal transformation. At the same time, the analysis also shows prospects: the introduction of e-governance, legal updates, creation of new control mechanisms and international cooperation form the basis for restoring and guaranteeing rights and freedoms in post-war Ukraine.

3. DISCUSSION

The results obtained indicate a profound transformation of Ukraine's legal system under martial law and an emergency situation in the field of protection of citizens' rights and freedoms. It is established that the legal guarantees enshrined in the Constitution and international acts require constant updating of implementation mechanisms in the context of threats related to military operations, some inconsistency in law enforcement practice and lack of institutional stability. Galagan et al.³⁸ substantiate the need for a flexible balance between limiting rights and ensuring the protection of fundamental freedoms in martial law, pointing to the risk of legal nihilism.

³⁷ Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. (1996). *Rights, Freedoms and Duties of a Person and a Citizen (Articles 21–68)*. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/254%D0%BA/96-%D0%B2%D1%80#Text>

³⁸ Galagan, O., Drozd, V., Galagan, S., & Drozd, V. (2023). Ensuring and restricting human rights and freedoms under martial law in Ukraine. *DIXI*, 25(2), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.16925/2357-5891.2023.02.13>

Yagunov³⁹ demonstrates how the realities of wartime affect criminal justice, in particular through the simplification of procedures, which may threaten fair trial. In turn, Gorbalskiy et al.⁴⁰ emphasize the challenges faced by the Ukrainian legal system in the context of the development of artificial intelligence, which, if not regulated, can become a tool for human rights violations.

The analysis also raises the problems of implementing fundamental guarantees, protection of vulnerable groups, legal protection in times of war. Mazur and Bortun⁴¹ emphasize the contradictions in the Ukrainian implementation of Article 6 of the European Convention on Human Rights, in particular in terms of the excessive length of trials. Simakova and Malyshko⁴² focus on the need for legal protection of street and abandoned children, pointing to the lack of national regulations that would meet international standards during the war. Tomkina et al.⁴³ show how restrictions concerning the guarantee of proper legal recourse amid lustration efforts create legal uncertainty, reducing trust in the legal system.

Modern scholarship also addresses the role of international law and organizations in overcoming systemic problems. Genoud⁴⁴ raises the issue of ethical inconsistency in the protection of human rights on the example of double standards of the international community, which is especially relevant in the case of Ukraine. Karpachova⁴⁵ highlights the role of international human rights structures in documenting rights violations in conflict, noting that their presence plays a key role in preventing systemic crimes from being ignored.

³⁹ Yagunov, D. (2022). Criminal justice system of Ukraine in the wartime: Impacts and challenges. *European Political and Law Discourse*, 9(4), 33–51. <https://doi.org/10.46340/eppd.2022.9.4.4>

⁴⁰ Gorbalskiy, V., Draliuk, I., Bondarchuk, V., Myroslavskyi, S., & Manhora, V. (2023). Ensuring Human Rights in the Era of Artificial Intelligence: Ukraine and Practice of ECHR. *Yuridika*, 38(3), 519–538. <https://doi.org/10.20473/ydk.v38i3.45134>

⁴¹ Mazur, O., & Bortun, K. (2023). Certain aspect of Article 6 @Right to a fair trial of the Convention on the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms. *Criminalistics and Forensics*, 68, 204–211. <https://doi.org/10.33994/kndise.2023.68.20>

⁴² Simakova, S., & Malyshko, I. (2023). International legal regulation of social protection of homeless and neglected children in conditions of war. *Uzhhorod National University Herald. Series: Law*, 1(76), 60–66. <https://doi.org/10.24144/2307-3322.2022.76.1.9>

⁴³ Tomkina, O., Mudra, O., & Rudei, V. (2022). Current problems of the realization of the right to effective remedies in the Ukrainian context of lustration. *Comparative Law Review*, 28, 435–458. <https://doi.org/10.12775/CLR.2022.015>

⁴⁴ Genoud, C. (2023). A Call for Self-criticism in Defending Values: From Human Rights in China to the War in Ukraine. *British Journal of Chinese Studies*, 13(1), 89–97. <https://doi.org/10.51661/bjocs.v13i1.221>

⁴⁵ Karpachova, N. I. (2021). The role of international human rights organisations in the context of the conflict in eastern Ukraine. *Journal of the National Academy of Legal Sciences of Ukraine*, 28(1), 24–31. <https://visnyk.kh.ua/en/journals/visnik-naprru-1-2021-r/rol-mizhnarodnikh-organizatsiy>

Particular attention in the discussion is paid to the effectiveness of applying to international judicial institutions, in particular the ECHR. Morska et al.⁴⁶ analyze new challenges in access to court, especially for victims of armed aggression, pointing to the need to simplify procedures. Erdoğan⁴⁷, in turn, considers the observance of the principle of equality in the field of refugee education, which is relevant for Ukraine as a country that receives and resettles internally displaced persons. Hromovchuk⁴⁸ raises the ethical and legal dilemma on the enforcement of the constitutional provision allowing euthanasia in Ukraine, which, against the backdrop of war, acquires new dimensions – the right to a decent life and death within the framework of full legal protection. Thus, ensuring the constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens in Ukraine in times of war requires constant updating of legal mechanisms, effective coordination with international law and the introduction of flexible institutional approaches to human protection.

CONCLUSION

4.

The study has shown that constitutionally enshrined rights and liberties of Ukraine's citizens remain legally guaranteed, but their actual implementation in the context of the armed aggression of the Russian Federation is subject to significant restrictions and challenges. Martial law, the need to ensure national security and mobilization preparedness have led to legitimate, but difficult restrictions on certain freedoms (freedom of movement, freedom of expression, the right to a fair trial, etc.) The most critical situations are in the temporarily occupied territories, where basic human rights are being violated on a massive scale.

At the same time, a key conclusion is the need for a comprehensive review and update of human rights protection mechanisms in the wartime and post-war period. Legislation on martial law, criminal and administrative law, and pre-trial defense mechanisms should be adapted to the standards of international humanitarian law and the judgments of the ECHR. The role of institutional human rights bodies needs to be strengthened: Ombudsman, courts, SSU, National Police, and the wider introduction of the practice of strategic judicial human rights protection. In the post-war period, the state should ensure guaranteed rehabilitation of affected citizens, effective compensation for violated rights and the creation of a new model of legal policy capable of ensuring sustainable democracy, the rule of law and real human protection in any crisis situation.

⁴⁶ Morska, N., Prysiazniuk, M., Luchkovska, S., Misiats, A., & Mikhnevych, L. (2022). The issue of the application to the European Court of Human Rights in the context of the Russian invasion of Ukraine. *Cuestiones Políticas*, 40(75), 868–878. <https://doi.org/10.46398/cuestpol.4075.52>

⁴⁷ Erdoğan, Z. (2023). Assessing the Criteria for Equality of the Right: Refugees' Higher Education from the Perspective of Human Rights. *Milli Egitim*, 52(237), 577–602. <https://doi.org/10.37669/milliegitim.1066619>

⁴⁸ Hromovchuk, M. (2021). Euthanasia in Ukraine: Issues of implementation of constitutional human rights. *Ukrainian Journal of Constitutional Law*, 2, 28–33. <https://doi.org/10.30970/jcl.2.2021.3>

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